

Nanostructured ZnO and TiO₂ Synthesis and Characterizations for Perovskite Solar Cell

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Abstract :

ZnO nanostructures play important role as potential material due to their wide bandgap, high electron mobility, excellent electronic and photonic properties. Various ZnO nanostructures are very much useful to improve electron extraction efficiency to replace TiO₂ as electron transport layer (ETL) in organic-Inorganic metal halide perovskite (CH₃NH₃PbX₃) based hybrid solar cell. Thin film perovskite solar cell draws technical interest for its high efficiency (25.2%, highest laboratory record) and low cost. Various forms of TiO₂ nanostructure plays important role due to its high extinction coefficient, high charge mobility, long carrier lifetime, and long carrier diffusion length. TiO₂ nanostructure plays dual role as a light absorbing material as well as an electron/hole transport layer in perovskite solar cell. Doped and undoped ZnO, undoped TiO₂ powder are synthesized by sol-gel route followed by rapid thermal annealing. Solution-processed ZnO and TiO₂ nanostructure at low temperatures yields different morphologies, and variation of band-gap with grain size. Structural and optical characterizations are carried out by XRD, SEM and UV-VIS spectroscopy respectively. ZnO is hexagonal-wurtzite polycrystalline II-VI compound semiconducting structure with (002) preferred orientation. Heat treated ZnO powder sample shows the miller indices of (100), (002), (102), and (004). Room temp TiO₂ powder samples show its amorphous phase but rutile and anatase phases are present after heat treatment.

Keywords: ZnO and TiO₂ Nanostructure, Sol-gel Technique, Rapid Thermal Annealing, X-ray diffraction, SEM, Perovskite Solar Cell

1. Introduction

In a planar perovskite-based solar cell (PSC), dense metal oxide film, such as ZnO is usually used to lower the work function of the modified TCO anode and as an electron-transport layer (to transfer the electrons and block the holes). The merits and demerits of the non-stoichiometry and presence of defect states in metal oxide thin film related to electron transport layer for planar PSC have not yet studied in detail. The intrinsic point defects in non-stoichiometric thin ZnO layer can create oxygen vacancy or Zinc interstitials or both. That can directly increase the charge density of ZnO which has good impact in enhancing the electronic properties of the metal oxides. In this scenario, the understanding of interface properties between ZnO/TiO₂ oxide and Methylammonium lead Iodide (CH₃NH₃PbI₃) perovskite is very much important. Better interface in PSC architecture can directly improve the electron transport mechanism (ETM) and ultimately enhanced photovoltaic performance in PSC can be achieved.

In PSC architecture three important layers are ETL, perovskite and hole transporting layer (HTL) respectively. The criteria of ETL are having good electron mobility, a wide bandgap and proper band gap matching with perovskite¹⁻⁶. RF-Magnetron sputtered (room temperature deposited on glass substrate) Al doped ZnO (ZnO:Al) and Ga doped ZnO (ZnO:Ga) thin films show 2.35×10^{-4} ohm-cm and 8.3×10^{-5} ohm-cm electrical resistivity along with high optical transmittance (above 85%) and haze

factor of 45-65% respectively. ZnO has electron mobility $200 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V.s}$ but TiO_2 has an electron mobility

of $1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V.s}$. TiO_2 and ZnO thin films are used as electron transport layers (ETL) reported elsewhere⁵⁻⁷. TiO_2 has well defined conduction band minima (CBM) of 4.2 eV relatively 0.3 eV lower than that of perovskite CBM. Therefore, TiO_2 can efficiently inject photogenerated electrons from a perovskite light absorber to ETM and block hole-transport. The CBM of ZnO is in intermediate position between TiO_2 and perovskite material (CBM of ZnO is higher than TiO_2 but still lower than perovskite light absorber), hence ZnO can be better ETL (have high efficiency of electron extraction and electron transport⁶) compared to TiO_2 .

Nano-structured mp- TiO_2 powder (Anatase and Rutile as well as mixed phase) shows high optical absorbance. Both (101) and (200) Anatase phase are mainly responsible for higher absorption coefficient in mixed TiO_2 powder. Organic Metal based Methylammonium lead Iodide ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$) perovskite was used as active layer in PSC architecture. Methylammonium lead Iodide ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$) perovskite coated $\text{TiO}_2/\text{ZnO:Ga}$ bi-layer thin films shows excellent electrical and optical properties. TiO_2 /Perovskite Interface can show interesting properties. Though the study of TiO_2/ZnO composite as ETM is rarely reported, but the combination of ZnO/ TiO_2 might have the advantage of both ETL and HTL. In this study, synthesis and electrical, optical and structural variation of TiO_2 coated ZnO thin film on $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite has been reported.

2. Experimental

Mesoporous titanium di-oxide (meso porus- TiO_2) coated ZnO:Ga film on glass substrate with two step spin coating technique. AZO thin films were used as seed layer for nano-structured ZnO or TiO_2 growth.

2.1. Sol-Gel synthesis of ZnO and TiO_2 Nanostructure

In our study, to prepare ZnO nanoparticle, 0.03 mol zinc acetate, and polyethylene glycol were dispersed in isopropyl alcohol and were dissolved in 50 mL de-ionized water. Finally, the solution was stirred at 90°C for 2 hrs and nano structured ZnO were prepared. Molar ratio of zinc acetate with polyethylene glycol was varied starting from 1:1 to 10:1.

For nanostructured TiO_2 synthesis, firstly, solution A was prepared by mixing 3 ml titanium tetra-isopropoxide (97 % Aldrich) and 12.5 ml of anhydrous ethanol (99.8 % Aldrich) while solution B contained 0.3 ml anhydrous ethanol, 0.25 ml distilled water, and 12 ml of acetic acid (99.7 % Aldrich). Solution B was then added drop by drop into solution A to obtain a clear transparent sol. After a few hours, the sol becomes milky and after several hours a gel is obtained. Subsequently, a drying step at 120°C is performed during 24 hrs to remove volatile solvents and then a xerogel is obtained and milled in an agate mortar. The resulting powder is calcinated at 500°C during 2 h ($5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$).

2.2. Characterization

The optical absorption of ZnO and TiO_2 nanostructure were measured by characterized by UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Eclipse, Varian, Paulo Alto, CA). X-ray diffraction was recorded by Rigaku D/max-2500 X-ray diffractometer (30 kV, 20 mA) with copper targets ($\lambda = 0.154059 \text{ nm}$). The structural characterization is also done by using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM, PHILIPS TECNAI G2 F20, 300 kV). Photosensitivity and the solar cell performance were measured by electrometer and solar simulators

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Variation of Optical Band gap

The molar ratio of zinc acetate with polyethylene glycol was varied from 1:1 to 10:1 during ZnO nanocrystals synthesis and grain size increases from 4 nm to 20 nm respectively, the variation of bandgap with grain size of the ZnO nanocrystals shown in fig. 1. ZnO nanoparticle has band gap (E_g) 4.03 eV, 3.44 eV and 3.26 eV for spherical shaped ZnO grains grain size 4 nm, 8 nm and 20 nm respectively. The minimum size (4nm) of ZnO nanocrystals

is achieved with 1:1 molar ratio of zinc acetate with polyethylene glycol, 8 nm for 2:1 ratio and 20 nm for 10:1 respectively.

Fig.1: Variation of Energy Bandgap of ZnO nanoparticle with Grainsize

3.2. Structural Studies of ZnO and TiO₂ Nanostructure

XRD spectrum shown in Fig. 2a, represents amorphous phase of TiO₂ samples but for Heat treated (at 500°C) TiO₂ nanoparticles have significant fractions of Anatase phase (XRD spectrum is not shown here) without having rutile peaks. TEM micrographs (Fig. 2b) establish the existence of crystalline phase of TiO₂ nanostructure at higher calcinations temperature. Amorphous to anatase phase transition occurs due to heat treatment (calcination temperature 500°C) for TiO₂ powder samples. Anatase phase of TiO₂ has a better photocatalytic activity due to the higher electron-hole pair lifetime compared to that of rutile structure. The versatile response in different activities of TiO₂ material is due to the direct/indirect bandgap for the transition from anatase to rutile phases.

Fig. 2: Structural Characterization of TiO₂ Nanostructure (a) XRD spectrum, (b) TEM micrograph

Nanocrystalline ZnO material shows multiple crystalline peaks along (100), (002), (102), and (004) respectively shown in the x-ray diffraction pattern (in fig. 3a). Here, (002) peak indicates the existence of hexagonal wurtzite structure along c-axis orientation and (100) represents the cubic phase of ZnO nanograins. The crystalline volume fraction of the cubic phase along (100) orientation is ~ 20% using the given formula⁵

$$\chi_{hkl} = \frac{I(100)}{I(100) + I(002) + I(102) + I(004)}$$

Fig. 3a: X-ray Diffraction Pattern for Sol-Gel Synthesized ZnO nanoparticle

The same for (002), (102) and (004) peaks are respectively given by 60%, 12% and 8% respectively.

Grain size variation and distribution of ZnO nanoparticles are shown in fig.3. One important observation was noted that there is no further increase of grain size as well as no absorption peak shift with the increase of molar ratio of zinc acetate and polyethylene glycol. Fig.3 shows the transmission electron micrograph of ZnO nanoparticles with different size 4 nm, 7nm and 20nm respectively where 4nm spherical shape has been reported elsewhere^{6,7}. Fig. 3b shows the dense distribution of distinct nanocrystalline grains in its nucleation site with interplaner spacing of ZnO nanocrystals is 2Å.

Fig.3b: Transmission Electron Micrograph of Sol-gel synthesized ZnO nanoparticles with Grain size (i) 4nm, (ii) 8nm and (iii) 20nm

3.3. Architecture of Perovskite solar cell

Perovskite Solar Cell (PSC) $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ is the new generation solar cell with enough scope in clean energy conversion due to versatile materials design capacity, cheap materials cost and materials availability. The main three components of PSC based solar cell architecture are an electron transporting material (ETM) layer, perovskite layer, and hole transport material (HTM) layer respectively. The ETM layer has crucial role for electron transport. ETM layer property such as band gap can be changed by suitable doping. Finally tuning and adjustment of energy band levels of ETM layer with active perovskite layer can help to enhance the photovoltaic performance.

3.4. Role of ZnO and TiO_2 for improvement of Perovskite solar cell

Both TiO_2 and ZnO can play common role as ETM materials. Transparent conducting ZnO

thin film can be used as front electrode. Meanwhile transparent conducting ZnO has good anti-reflecting properties that can reduce the scattering loss as window material. TiO₂ has versatile materials properties such as photo activity, high stability, non-toxicity and also band gap tuning capability by doping. TiO₂ has Lower valence band minima compared to perovskite materials. On the other hand ZnO has intermediate valence band minima (i.e. VBM position is higher than that of TiO₂ but lower than CBM of perovskite materials). That is why electron transfer from ZnO valence band to perovskite conduction band is more easier than that of TiO₂ materials. Formation of TiO₂ and ZnO composite structure as ETM has more advantageous in perovskite solar cell. Better photosensitivity and the solar cell performance have been reported^{7,8} with TiO₂/ZnO composition as ETM layer in perovskite solar cell.

4. Conclusion

ZnO and TiO₂ nanostructure with desired tunable bandgap and grain size have been successfully deposited and characterized. The XRD result showed existence of different crystalline phases of ZnO nanostructure without any impurity and amorphous structure of sol-gel synthesized TiO₂ materials. TEM micrograph shows internal morphology of ZnO and TiO₂ nanocrystallines. The bandgap of the ZnO samples were in between 3.26 eV to 4.02 eV whereas the same for TiO₂ is 3.6eV respectively. On the experimental basis supporting materials properties electron transfer mechanism for both ZnO and TiO₂ has been compared. The Perovskite Solar Cell performance with ZnO and TiO₂ not yet reported.

References

1. Tonui P, Oseni S O, Sharma G, Yan Q and Tessema Mola G 2018 Perovskites photovoltaic solar cells: An overview of current status Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 91 1025–44
2. Ramamoorthy K., Sanjeeviraja C., *et al.*, Preparation and characterization of ZnO thin films on InP by laser-molecular beam epitaxy technique for solar cells. *Journal of Crystal Growth*. 2001; 226 (3): 281–6p.
3. Zou Bingsuo, Wang Z L, Volkov V. Optical Properties of Amorphous ZnO, CdO and PdO Nanoclusters in Solution. *Chem. Mater.* 1999; 11(2): 3037–43p.
4. Sarkar S., Patra S., Bera S.K., *et al.* Water repellent ZnO nanowire arrays synthesized by simple solvothermal technique. *Materials Letters*. 2010; 64(3): 460–2p.
5. Yin X, Xu Z, Guo Y, Xu P and He M 2016 Ternary Oxides in the TiO₂–ZnO System as Efficient Electron-Transport Layers for Perovskite Solar Cells with Efficiency over 15% ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces 8 29580–7
6. Mohamad Noh M F, Teh C H, Daik R, Lim E L, Yap C C, Ibrahim M A, Ahmad Ludin N, Mohd Yusoff A R bin, Jang J and Mat Teridi M A 2018 The architecture of the electron transport layer for a perovskite solar cell *Journal of Materials Chemistry C* 6 682–712
7. Yang G, Tao H, Qin P, Ke W and Fang G 2016 Recent progress in electron transport layers for efficient perovskite solar cells *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 4 3970–90.
8. D. Liu and Kelly, *Nat. Photonics*, 2014, 8, 133

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Dr. Rajesh Das did Masters in Physics with specialization in Electronics from Jadavpur University. Dr. Das was engaged in his Ph.D work in the field of Transparent Conducting Thin films for Solar Cell applications from the department of Energy Research Unit, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science and awarded by Ph.D from Jadavpur University in 2005. He joined as Research Engineer in the department of Surface Technology Division, Singapore Institute of Manufacturing Technology to develop Advanced Optical Coating in 2005. After completion this tenure, Dr. Das joined as Post-doctoral Research Associate in the Department of Electrical Engineering, Computer and Future Energy, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, New York (USA) for the tenure 2007-2008. Dr. Das joined as Senior Lecturer in the Department of Applied Science, Haldia Institute of

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Swapnadeep Guria passed his Higher Secondary Examination from D.A.V Public School, Haldia and secured 90.2% marks in CBSE board in the year of 2022. Right now he is pursuing B.Tech program in the discipline of Chemical Engineering in Haldia Institute of Technology (Autonomy). He has presented a number of national/international seminar and conference (APPSCICON 22 – An Interdisciplinary National Conference in MAKAUT, The Scope of Intra and Intercontinental Research and Collaboration in Applied Science and

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Namita Dutta Gupta

Dr. Namita Dutta Gupta did Masters in Physics with specialization in Electronics from Kalyani University in 1996. Dr. Dutta Gupta was engaged in Post-M.Sc program in Inter University Consortium, Kolkata during 1997-98. Immediately after completion of Post M.Sc program, she was engaged as doctoral researcher for the development of Amorphous Silicon Thin films material for Solar Cell applications in the department of Energy Research Unit, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science for the tenure of 1998 -2004 and awarded by Ph.D from Jadavpur University in 2004. She joined as Post-doctoral Research Fellow in Laboratoire de Génie Electrique de Paris, France for the period of 2004-2006.

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